

Kinetics of Oxidation of Benzilic Acid by Potassium Peroxydisulphate Catalysed by Ag(I) Ion

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The Ag(I) catalysed oxidation of benzilic acid was found to be first order with respect to peroxydisulphate and Ag(I) ions and independent of the concentration of benzilic acid. The rate is inhibited by allyl acetate and is unaffected by the change of dielectric constant. The effect of certain salts on rate has been evaluated. The rate-laws have been explained on the basis of a free-radical mechanism involving Ag(II).

IN recent years, work on the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of a variety of substances, both organic and inorganic, by peroxydisulphate ion, has greatly increased. The catalysed as well as non catalysed oxidation by peroxydisulphate has been reviewed by Wilmarth and House¹⁻². Much interest has been shown towards the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by peroxydisulphate, both in catalysed and uncatalysed conditions³⁻⁴. A survey of the literature reveals that no work is reported on the oxidation of benzilic acid by peroxydisulphate. In this communication the results on the kinetic study of the Ag(I) catalysed oxidation of benzilic acid by peroxydisulphate are reported.

Benzilic acid (Extra Pure, Fluka), silver nitrate (BDH, AR) and potassium peroxydisulphate (AR) were used. The kinetic studies were carried out in aqueous acetic acid media. The rate of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted peroxydisulphate by the iodometric procedure of Koltthoff and Carr⁵. The oxidation of benzilic acid afforded benzophenone as the product of oxidation, as characterised by its 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone.

The reactions were observed to follow first order rate laws with respect to $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ as evidenced by the linearity of the plots of $\log [S_2O_8^{2-}]_t$ vs. time over 70 to 80% of the reaction. Further the reaction was found to be independent of the concentration of the organic substrate (Table 1).

The reaction also exhibits first-order dependence on $[Ag(I)]$ as shown by the linear plots of $\log k_t$ vs. $\log [Ag(I)]$ with a slope of nearly unity. Further, a plot of k_t against $[Ag(I)]$ passes through the origin, showing that the uncatalysed decomposition of peroxydisulphate is negligible (Fig. 1).

The salt effect was studied by the addition of different concentrations of potassium sulphate and potassium nitrate. Changes in the ionic strength decreases the rate of reaction, thus indicating that the salt effect is negative (Table 2). It is interesting to note that the nitrate ion exhibits a stronger inhibitory

TABLE 1. DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON BENZILIC ACID

Solvent—30% HOAc; $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.004M$;
 $[Ag(I)] = 4 \times 10^{-4}M$; Temp. 35°, $\mu = 0.2$

[Benzilic Acid] M	$k_t \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1}$
0.016	11.99
0.020	11.99
0.024	12.05
0.028	12.67
0.032	12.55
0.040	11.90
0.048	11.82

influence on the rate of the reaction compared to sulphate. This suggests the operation of specific salt effect.

Allyl acetate, an effective captor for SO_4^- inhibits the oxidation considerably⁶. The reaction was carried out in different acetic acid water solvent mixtures. The rate of the reaction is not susceptible to any variation with the change in dielectric constant of the medium.

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE RATE OF REACTION

Solvent—30% HOAc, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.004 M$
 [Benzilic acid] = 0.02M, $[Ag^+] = 0.0004 M$,
 Temp. 35°.

Ionic strength	Electrolytes used	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec.}^{-1}$
0.0496	(a) K_2SO_4	21.49
	(b) KNO_3	19.95
0.0868	(a) K_2SO_4	19.19
	(b) KNO_3	18.42
0.1612	(a) K_2SO_4	14.20
	(b) KNO_3	10.36
0.20	(a) K_2SO_4	11.98
	(b) KNO_3	9.21

The reaction was carried out in four different temperatures. The Arrhenius equation was found to be valid in the temperature range studied. The energy and entropy of activation were calculated to be 19.30 Kcal/mole and -15.80 e.u. respectively. [k_{25} , k_{30} , k_{35} and k_{40} are $4.22 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$, $7.11 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$, $11.99 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$ and $18.80 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$ respectively].

These observations are strongly indicative of the operation of a chain mechanism involving $SO_4^{\cdot -}$ and other free radicals in the oxidation process.

The observed rate law $-d[S_2O_8^{2-}]/dt = k_1[S_2O_8^{2-}][Ag(I)]$ suggests that the rate-determining step between $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and $Ag(I)$ ion yields one or more intermediates capable of rapidly oxidising the reductant in subsequent fast steps. Regarding the nature of the silver species, the recent evidences in literature point to the fact that in aqueous acid solutions, the existence of $Ag(II)$ is more likely than the higher state of silver species⁷. The rate expression may be explained in terms of different free radicals as follows:

Applying steady state principle we have,

$$\frac{-d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = \left(\frac{k_1 k_3 k_4}{k_5} \right)^{1/2} [Ag^+][S_2O_8^{2-}] = k_1 [Ag^+][S_2O_8^{2-}].$$

The proposed mechanism leads to the observed rate law and explains the dependence of the rate constant on the first power of $[Ag^+]$.

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